

REFLECTION OF THE DYSTOPIC GENRE IN THE WORKS OF ENGLISH WRITERS

Madinakhon Irsalieva

National University of Uzbekistan

Email: Irsaliyevamadina92@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.19381075>

Keywords: *dystopia, English literature, totalitarianism, technology, personal freedom.*

This article is devoted to highlighting the formation and evolution of the dystopian genre in English literature. The work of English writers of the 20th and 21st centuries analyzes the relationship of dystopia to society, power, technology, and human freedom. Along with classic authors such as George Orwell, Aldous Huxley, and H.G. Wells, the works of Margaret Atwood and Kazuo Ishiguro reveal a modern interpretation of dystopian views. The results of the study substantiate the fact that dystopian literature has a warning and critical nature.

Dystopian literature is one of the important directions of modern artistic thought, which serves to express in artistic form the negative consequences of social development. This genre depicts the erosion of human rights, freedoms, and moral values through a future or alternative model of society. Dystopia in English literature developed under the influence of dramatic social and political processes, especially in the 20th century. The acceleration of industrialization, the centralization of political governance, and the uncontrolled development of science created the basis for the emergence of dystopian works. By the 21st century, digital technologies, environmental problems, and bioethics have further expanded the themes of dystopian literature.

1. The essence and characteristics of the dystopian genre.

Dystopia is a literary genre that describes a non-ideal model of society, based on oppression and control. It often contradicts utopian views and shows the dangers that humanity may face. English writers have used dystopia as a means of social criticism and warning. The characteristics of this genre include the following:

Control and repression: Unlimited control by the government or other forces, totalitarian regimes.

Loss of freedom: Personal freedoms, thinking, and emotions are limited.

Negative effects of technology: Technology is used to control people or make their lives worse.

Social inequality: Society is divided into layers, the gap between the rich and the poor is large.

Loss of nature: Ecological problems, loss of contact with nature.

Hopelessness: The characters of the work often fight against a system that is unable to change, resulting in despair.

2. The problem of political control in the works of George Orwell. George Orwell's novel "1984" embodies a sharp criticism of totalitarian society. The work describes the complete subjugation of the individual by the state through the destruction of freedom of thought, constant surveillance and falsification of information. The dystopian model created by Orwell reveals the consequences of the unlimited power of political power.

3. Aldous Huxley and technological control. In the novel "Brave New World", Aldous Huxley describes a society of humanity controlled by technology and consumption. In this work,

freedom is limited not by open violence, but by means of artificial happiness and pleasure. Huxley's dystopia shows the spiritual degradation of man and the weakening of his ability to think independently.

4. *Dystopian ideas in the works of H.G. Wells.* H.G. Wells' science fiction works depict negative visions of a future society, raising issues of social inequality and the misuse of science. The Time Machine depicts the division of humanity into classes and its decline in a dystopian spirit.

5. *21st century English writers and a new interpretation of dystopia.* In 21st century English literature, the dystopian genre has been enriched with global problems. Margaret Atwood's novels "The Handmaid's Tale" and "Oryx and Crake" highlight gender inequality, environmental disasters, and the dangerous consequences of biotechnology. The author builds dystopia on the basis of processes that can occur in real life. Kazuo Ishiguro's "Never Let Me Go" raises the issue of the life and moral rights of people created through cloning. The dystopian environment is conveyed through calm and emotional images, and the moral responsibility of humanity is questioned. Kazuo Ishiguro's novel Never Let Me Go differs from the classic dystopian genre examples: it illuminates the subtle but profound violation of human rights, freedom, and biological control with an intellectual axis rather than the traditional depiction of totalitarian rule or open repression. The dystopian society created in the work is depicted on the basis of a "reconstructed" modern social reality, where scientific progress - in particular, the technology of human cloning - violates ethical boundaries and weakens human values.

The heroes of the novel - clones - are created to become organ donors, so-called "donors" for them. Society accepts this process as an integral part of normal life, so the clones are deprived of the opportunity to fight against their tragic fate or challenge others. Their lives are determined by biological function, and personal choice and freedom are strictly limited.

Biological control and social manipulation

Despite the fact that the dystopian society has achieved sufficient technological progress, this progress is disconnected from moral responsibility. Despite the fact that the clones are sentient beings, capable of love, friendship and patience - their lives are used as a source of prolonging health for others. They are born into a society where their fate is "predestined" and are prepared to become organ donors. The fate of humanity as the slippery victims of dystopia

In the novel, dystopia focuses not only on political oppression or repression, but also reveals human problems on a personal level - memory, love, loss and degradation. The clones are accepted by society as non-human, but they experience emotional experiences and complex aspects of life - which is the most tragic aspect of dystopia.

In conclusion, it can be said that the dystopian genre in English literature is an important direction that exposes negative trends in society in artistic form. While 20th-century writers focused on depicting political and technological oppression, 21st-century authors have enriched dystopia with global and moral problems. Dystopian works encourage the reader to think critically and uphold human values.

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